

8 Theory – Using The Coupling Constant Equation To Show SUSY Is Only Partly Correct

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Abstract:

By using the new framework of the 8-theory, and in particular the primordial coupling constant equation in its second representation, i.e. spin, it is possible to extrapolate an insight on the matter of SUSY. The subject was analyzed in the PW duality in the thesis. The new framework indicate that it is possible to vary the spin of bosons and so allocate them a spin of a fermion, that is the underlining principle behind the problem of measurement in quantum theories. Such variations however do not transform a massless boson into a positive mass particle. The conclusion than is that we long discovered the SUSY, but failed to recognize it and failed to understand the idea.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{0}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{2}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

Equations (1) to (3) describe the coupling constant equation in its first representation, net variations. In the thesis we found four representations. The second representation was about the shift to the prime critical line and so represent each term:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3.0)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3.1)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3.2)$$

In the part describing particle wave duality we made a measurement on the photon, by another photon, so in the framework we varied equation (3.1) an added an additional net variation (+5).

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + 5 \quad (3.3)$$

$$\left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3.4)$$

$$2n + 1 \rightarrow 2n + \frac{3}{2} \quad (3.5)$$

So in this framework it is possible to vary the spin of a boson, but that does not yield a fermion but rather make a boson behave like a fermion. Synonymous to the cancelation of the interference In QM. So overall SUSY is something we know about for a long period time, just failed to recognize. Susy is in a question mark at this very moment regarding the subject of fermions into bosons. Its seems impossible to vary the spin of a fermion by collusion with another fermion due to their anti-commutation relation. Therefore, in that sense SUSY is not correct. Overall, the fact that we can vary the spin of a boson by half unit spin means cancelation of interference.

The idea is only partly correct, and the implications were interrupted in the wrong way. Varying the spin of the boson did not yield a kind of a boson but rather changed its nature, from wavelike to particle like. Such process can not be performed on fermions, as one believe. Two main reasons, the Pauli Exclusion Principle and the Poincare tensions. The fermion is enticed to the nuclei despite its probabilistic nature, and second, its anti-commutation relation ensure its nature to stay as it is in contrasted to bosons which are much more flexible. This paper is not included in the thesis of the 8-theory as it is elusive and confusing and the author himself changed his mind from his previous papers about SUSY being completely wrong, so this paper and it's stand too could vary with time.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)